

The Exchange Processes in Zinc Complexes of *o*-Vanillin Salicyloylhydrazone as studied by Two-Dimensional NMR

B. V. AGARWALA^a, V. PURI^a, G. A. NAGANAGOWDA^b and C. L. KHETRAPAL^{*b}

^aDepartment of Postgraduate Studies & Research in Chemistry, R. D. University, Jabalpur-482 001

^bSophisticated Instruments Facility, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore-560 012

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Zinc forms two types of complexes with *o*-vanillin salicyloylhydrazone. The ¹H and ¹³C nmr studies suggest that it coordinates with azomethine nitrogen, the carbonyl oxygen and with one or both of the phenolic oxygens. The ¹H-¹H and ¹H decoupled ¹³C-¹³C two-dimensional nuclear Overhauser and exchange spectra show that there is an exchange between the two types of complexes.

Mixed ligand complexes wherein the metal ions are bound to biochemically important ligands, have aroused interest as models for the metalloenzymes^{1,2}. Zinc complexes are of particular interest in this respect due to their biological

simpler ligands⁴⁻⁶. Zinc complexes with *o*-vanillin derivatives in particular have been of considerable interest^{7,8}.

Nmr spectroscopy is one of the most powerful techniques for obtaining information on the struc-

Fig. 1. ¹H-¹H 2Q FCOSEY spectrum of the zinc complexes at 400.13 MHz.

activities³. Many functions of zinc metalloenzymes have been mimicked by making complexes with

tural and dynamical properties of the molecules. In the field of coordination chemistry, nmr spectros-

copy is of vital importance as the sites of the coordinating centres are reflected clearly in the changes of their chemical shifts and/or of those sites which are close to the coordinating centres^{5,9}. Especially, the advent of newer techniques in nmr makes it possible to investigate dynamical processes like conformational and chemical exchanges¹⁰⁻¹². The present communication reports the results on the complexes of zinc with *o*-vanillin salicyloylhydrazone (oVSH) by one- and two-dimensional nmr spectroscopy.

Results and Discussion

¹H spectrum of the sample (Fig. 1) shows two

analysis of the spectrum of the pure ligand. The labile NH and the OH protons of complex 1 were assigned by one-dimensional NOE experiments. The chemical shifts of various resonances for both the complexes are given in Table 1. The shifts of the pure ligand are also included in the table for comparison.

Analysis of the ¹³C-resonances corresponding to complex 1 was made using the HETCOSY and COLOC experimental data together with the comparison of the shifts of those of the pure ligand. A typical spectrum of HETCOSY is shown in Fig. 3. The chemical shifts of all the resonances are given

Fig. 2. ¹H-¹H NOESY spectrum of the zinc complexes at 400 13 MHz. The cross-peaks in the squares indicate the chemical exchange between the two types of complexes.

sets of signals in the ratio 12 : 1, corresponding to two types of complexes formed with zinc. Analysis of the resonances of both major (complex 1) and the minor (complex 2) sets was made making use of ¹H-¹H 2QF-COSY (Fig. 1), ¹H-¹H NOESY (Fig. 2) spectral data and with the knowledge of the

in Table 2. The shifts of the pure ligand resonances are also included in the table for comparison. Neither the HETCOSY nor the COLOC experiments could be used for the analysis of the signals for complex 2 due to very low intensity as seen in the heteronuclear COSY (Fig. 3) spectrum. Therefore

^{13}C - ^{13}C NOESY spectrum was made use of to analyse these signals (Fig. 4). It is clear from the figure that the weak diagonal signals of the complex **2** are not seen in the spectrum, whereas the corresponding cross-peaks are clearly visible. The cross-peaks observed are solely due to chemical exchange of the ligands in the two complexes. The nuclei which do not show any cross-peaks indicate that the resonances of such carbons in both the complexes are overlapping. Chemical shifts of complex **2** thus obtained are included in the Table 2.

All the proton resonances of complex **1** except those of the OH proton, shift to high field compared to those of the pure ligand (Table 1), the shifts of the signals of the vanillin ring being more than those of the salicyloyl ring. Also the signals of the carbons 6, 8 and 9 are shifted compared to those of the ligands from 147.32, 149.02 and 164.60 ppm to 159.90, 155.42 and 170.25 ppm respectively. This indicates that the phenolic oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and the carbonyl oxygen are coordinating with the metal ion. The shift of the carbon at position 15 remains almost unaltered for complex **1** (Table 2). In addition, the rest of the carbons of the salicyloyl ring do not shift considerably. These observations indicate that the oxygen attached to the carbon-15 is not coordinating to the metal, leading to the following structure for the complex **1**.

Complex 1

All the proton resonances of the ligand *o*VSH corresponding to complex **2** also shift to high field compared to those of complex **1** (Table 1), except the signal of the proton labelled 11, which has shifted to low field. The up-field shift of the proton 2 is unusually large. It has shifted from 7.17 in the pure ligand to 5.55 ppm. The protons 3 and 4 have shifted from 6.88 and 7.05 to 6.10 and 6.66 ppm respectively (Table 1). Also the ^{13}C resonance of the carbons 6, 8 and 9, like in the case of complex

1, have shifted compared to those of the pure ligand from 147.32, 149.02 and 164.60 ppm to 159.90, 154.54 and 170.25 ppm. In addition, the carbon

TABLE 1— ^1H CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF *o*-VANILLIN SALICYLOYLHYDRAZONE AND ITS ZINC COMPLEXES **1** AND **2** DISSOLVED IN DIMETHYL SULPHOXIDE*

Proton	Ligand	Complex 1	Complex 2
2	7.17	6.85	5.55
3	6.88	6.40	6.10
4	7.05	6.79	6.66
7	3.82	3.72	3.64
8	8.69	8.52	8.17
11	7.89	7.87	8.07
12	6.97	6.82	6.61
13	7.47	7.26	7.23
14	6.99	6.81	6.70
OH	12.00	12.07	—
NH	10.80	—	12.72

* Values are in ppm down-field of TMS.

labelled 15 which shifted negligibly in complex **1**, has shifted down-field to 168.24 ppm in complex **2** (Table 2). These observations suggest that ligand *o*VSH is most probably coordinating with metal with its four coordinating sites, the three sites are as in the case of complex **1** and the fourth one being the phenolic oxygen of the salicyloyl group. The unusual up-field shift of proton 2 to 5.55 ppm is probably due to steric effects. This is further supported by the fact that the carbons labelled 2 in both the complexes have almost the same chemical shifts (125.37 ppm for complex **1** and 124.88 ppm for the complex **2**), whereas the shifts for the corresponding protons are considerably different (6.85 ppm for complex **1** and 5.55 ppm for complex **2**). The proposed structure for the complex **2** is given below.

Complex 2

^1H - ^1H and ^{13}C - ^{13}C NOESY spectra of the complexes (Figs. 2 and 4) show that the ligands *o*VSH in both the complexes are exchanging.

Exchange cross-peaks are observed between the corresponding signals of the ligands in the two complexes. For ^1H - ^1H NOESY spectrum (Fig. 2), the cross-peaks in the squares indicate the exchange between the signals of the two complexes. For the ^{13}C - ^{13}C NOESY spectrum (Fig. 4), all the cross-peaks are due to exchange of ligands in both the complexes.

Conclusion : The formation of two types of complexes of zinc with *o*-vanillin salicyloylhydra-

o-Vanillin salicyloylhydrazone (*o*VSH) : Salicyloyl hydrazide was prepared by the standard method¹³. Equimolar ethanolic solutions of salicyloyl hydrazide (0.05 mol, 7.61 g) and *o*-vanillin (0.05 mol, 7.60 g) were mixed together and refluxed over a water-bath for 4–5 h. The separated solid was washed several times with ethanol followed by ether. It was recrystallised from acetone and dried in vacuum to obtain the ligand in its pure form.

Fig. 3. ^1H - ^{13}C heteronuclear COSY spectrum of the zinc complexes at 400.13 and 100.61 MHz for ^1H and ^{13}C respectively. Cross-peaks for complex 2 are not seen due to its low intensity compared to that of complex 1.

zone have been established by ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectroscopy. Use of two-dimensional nmr experiments has been made in order to establish the sites of coordination and study the exchange processes in the complexes.

Experimental

Methyl salicylate, hydrazine hydrate, *o*-vanillin (all Sisco) and $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck) were used. Other chemicals and solvents used were of reagent grade.

The zinc complexes : The complex was synthesised by mixing the solution of *o*VSH (0.005 mol, 1.43 g) in minimum quantity of DMF and an aqueous solution of zinc acetate (0.005 mol, 1.10 g). The mixture was made to about 70 cm³ by adding ethanol and then refluxed on a heating mantle for 4 h. On cooling the yellow solid obtained was washed with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 (yield 80% with respect to the ligand with structure given below) :

Ligand

Nmr studies : Deuterated dimethyl sulphoxide (Sigma) was used as the solvent. The ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra were recorded at 400.13 and 100.61 MHz on an AMX-400 FTNMR spectrometer.

TABLE 2- ^{13}C CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF *o*-VANILLIN SALICYLOYLHYDRAZONE AND ITS ZINC COMPLEXES 1 AND 2 DISSOLVED IN DIMETHYL SULPHOXIDE*

Carbon	Ligand	Complex 1	Complex 2
1	118.88	118.22	118.22
2	120.86	125.37	124.88
3	119.10	112.63	112.63
4	114.00	112.87	112.87
5	148.08	151.72	151.72
6	147.32	159.90	159.90
7	55.88	55.64	55.64
8	149.02	155.42	154.54
9	164.60	170.25	170.25
10	115.61	118.23	116.81
11	128.57	128.67	131.38
12	119.02	117.91	113.54
13	133.99	131.67	132.54
14	117.34	116.52	122.97
15	159.12	159.74	168.24

* Shifts are in ppm down-field of TMS signal.

A $\sim 0.07\text{ M}$ solution of the zinc complex of *o*VSH was studied in dimethyl sulphoxide. Normal ^1H and ^{13}C one-dimensional as well as the deuterium exchanged experiments were performed. The one-dimensional nuclear Overhauser enhancement (NOE) experiments, phase sensitive ^1H - ^1H double quantum filtered COSY (2QF-COSY) (14-16), Nuclear Overhauser and Exchange (NOESY), and ^1H decoupled ^{13}C - ^{13}C NOESY¹⁷ spectra, magnitude mode ^1H - ^{13}C heteronuclear COSY (HETCOSY)¹⁸ and ^1H - ^{13}C correlation of long range coupling (COLOC)¹⁹ spectra were studied for the complex.

For the 2QF-COSY, 512 free induction decays with t_1 increments each of 1024 points, 8 scans and recycle delay of 1 s were collected and Fourier transformed along both the dimensions after multiplying by sine-square window function shifted by $\pi/2$, with zero filling the t_1 -points to 1024. For the ^1H - ^1H NOESY spectrum, mixing time of 300 ms was used. 512 free induction decays in the t_1 -dimension each of 1024 points, 64 scans and recycle delay of 1 s were collected. The t_1 points were zero filled to 1024. Fourier transformation was

Fig. 4. ^1H decoupled ^{13}C - ^{13}C NOESY spectrum of the zinc complexes at 100.61 MHz.

performed along both the dimensions after multiplying by sine-square window function shifted by $\pi/2$. For ^1H decoupled ^{13}C - ^{13}C NOESY, 512 free induction decays with t_1 increments each of 1024 points, 128 scans, recycle delay of 1 s and mixing time of 400 ms were collected. The t_1 points were zero filled to 1024 and Fourier transformed after multiplying by Gaussian broadening function to observe the weaker signals, with line broadening (LB) = -0.96 and GB = 0.01 along both the dimensions. HETCOSY and COLOC experiments were performed collecting 512 t_1 points each of 1024 points, 128 scans and recycle delay of 1 s in both the cases. Fourier transformation was performed in magnitude mode with zero filling the t_1 points to 1024. The window function used was sine-square

shifted by $\pi/2$ along both the dimensions in each of the cases.

Spectral widths of 4000 and 17500 Hz were used for ^1H and ^{13}C respectively, for the corresponding two-dimensional experiments.

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